

International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education

www.ijete.org.pk

Research Article

Co-Curricular Activities of Secondary Schools: A Comparative study of Public and Private Schools

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 5-May-23 Revised: 18-Jun-23 Accepted: 3-Jul-23 Published: 9-Jul-23	This study was conducted to examine the comparison between the co-curricular activities in public and private schools in Pretoria city, South Africa. This study was descriptive in nature and survey method was used for the study. There were total two hundred and fifty-six (256) female teachers from private and public secondary schools of Pretoria city. A questionnaire used as a research instrument to collect data from the female teachers of the public and private secondary schools. The researcher collected the data personally from teachers of secondary school in Pretoria city. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) used to analyzes the data and simple mean, frequency, and percentage used for the analysis of data. It was found that sports activities develop physical strength of students. It is recommended that teachers may make the morning assembly a center of interest by giving it strength and spirit.
Keywords:	Co-curricular activities, Writing competitions, Debate competitions, Sports, Drawing, Painting, Public and private schools
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How to Cite:	Saifi, I. L. (2023). Co-Curricular Activities of Secondary Schools: A Comparative study of Public and Private Schools. <i>International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education</i> , 1(1), 48-60.

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INTRODUCTION

Education is a process that develops the personality and inherent capabilities of a child. So, Education must be designed to help each person reach their maximum potential and be given the opportunity to succeed in life to the extent that their innate skills will allow. The child enters the school with mental, physical, spiritual, social, and occupational needs, and modern education understands that he must be educated in all of these. It is acknowledged that these activities are effective tools for helping students form healthy attitudes, routines, interests, and values. The effective management of extracurricular activities in schools will help to the greatest extent possible in achieving this goal (Yaseen, 2017).

Education is a continuous and life-long process; and should contribute not only to the mental but also to the physical capabilities of the students. The term "Co-curricular activities" has correctly taken the place of the term "Extra-curricular activities." After a long day of mental labor, the kids need a physical refreshment. In addition to having high physical health, the children who participate in these activities have also demonstrated that they are academically superior to those who do not. (Memon, 2007). Co-curricular activities are now considered to be the intrinsic part of the educational endeavor in a school. Recently, they were referred to as extracurricular activities. Yet, these are increasingly accepted as a standard component of curricula for a child's total education. They are now referred to as co-curricular activities rather than extracurricular activities. Since they are an essential component of the school curriculum, they have been rebranded as co-curricular activities due to their significance in education. Hence, co-curricular and academic activities are carried out together (Ahmed, 2015).

Co-curricular activities allow kids to showcase their diverse abilities. In the absence of activity facilities, many of the children's potentials are likely to go untapped. After their exploration, they hone and grow their talent. Sports, games, and other extracurricular activities help youngsters develop physically. They are particularly beneficial for children's motor and sensory development. The boys and girls must successfully engage in social activities in order to become socially well-adjusted, according to the current understanding of transfer of training. The government sector is having trouble offering all residents a free, affordable education because of the expanding population. As a result, the private sector is making a significant contribution to meeting the educational needs of the expanding population. Private schools are wholly owned by individuals or organizations rather than the state, and they charge a monthly, per-semester, or annual tuition. Owners of these private institutions pay the government an annual registration fee. The issue of providing pupils with a high-quality education that meets their needs comes as a result of the increased competition between private and public schools. As compared to government schools, the private schools provide students with more co-curricular activities (Muhammad, 2012).

In Pretoria city, South Africa, public schools perform lower than private ones. Private schools are becoming more popular, as a result of their higher standards of operation and higher levels of instruction. Private schools achieve better results than public ones (Hussain, 2018). The lack of infrastructure, the poorer organization, and the poorer quality of instruction in the public school system are the primary causes of this demanding tendency. Private sector education providers aim to improve the quality of instruction in public schools. Co-curricular activities are crucial for kids since they aid in both their academic and overall development. The school is crucial in planning the various extracurricular and curricular programs. Teachers and the institution's leadership are

key players in motivating students to participate in extracurricular activities. The teacher's dedication is crucial for helping students grow in co-curricular activities in schools. The co-curricular activities of pupils are currently not given great priority for a variety of reasons. There are few opportunities for students to participate in extracurricular activities. Therefore, the researcher felt that there is need to compare the study of co-curricular activities of public and private school Pretoria city, South Africa.

Research objectives

1. To find out the co-curricular activities offered by public secondary schools.
2. To identify the co-curricular activities offered by private secondary schools.
3. To compare the co-curricular activities offered by public and private secondary schools.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Activities

Classroom activities will be activities finished by understudy inside the class as a feature of applying or doing the functional piece of the example subsequent to paying attention to the hypothetical part which is introduced by the educator. Activities outside class empower students to investigate more information through visiting libraries, answering utilizing ecological, utilizing electronic projects, and getting to significant destinations of web (Mukesh, 2013).

The term classroom activities apply to an extensive variety of expertise-based games, techniques and intelligent activities that help understudies' instructive turn of events. The objective of movements of every kind is to improve understudies' grasping, expertise, or viability in a particular region by drawing in numerous styles of learning. School activities additionally inject fun into advancing as well as reinforce understudy certainty and the capacity to basically think (Karim, 2011).

Curricular Activities

Activities that are part of the curriculum are referred to as curricula. The examples of courses include Calculation Bats, Prediction Bees, Pupil Meetings, and Institute Drama. Fundamentally, curricular or educational activities are communication activities centered around the predetermined educational choices. In modest terms it can be assumed that are accepted inside the schoolroom, in the workroom, workspace or in reading room known as "curricular activities." These are essential part of the whole instructional platform. Because in the association of these activities or packages there lies energetic participation of the teaching staff of the learning institution (Gajjar, 2014).

Co-curricular Activities

Co-curricular activities will be activities that happen outside the classroom however support or supplement classroom educational program here and there. They are ungraded and offer no kind of academic credit, yet they truly give complementary learning of some construction. Cases of co-curricular activities could incorporate student council, school sports gatherings, math clubs, chess clubs, capacity shows, spelling bumble bees, composing competitions, examines, mock starters, school papers, and performance manifestations. These activities occur outside the standard classroom and recommendation no grade or educational credit, yet they give reinforcing direction and preparing to students (Husain, 2012). Activities upheld or recognized by a school or college

which are not piece of the educational instructive arrangement but instead are recognized to be a crucial piece of the presence of an enlightening foundation. Co-curricular activities incorporate games, school gatherings, student paper, etc. They may moreover be classed as 'extracurricular' i.e., activities carried on outer the standard course of survey, activities outside the standard commitments of an errand, as extra class activities. To lay it out plainly, co-curricular activities will be activities that are advantageous to classroom training. They are not straightforwardly connected to the course educational program, yet they structure a significant piece of it by permitting understudies to take part in the opportunities for growth. Generally, co-curricular activities don't convey grades however the understudy's presentation in these activities are displayed in the report card (Astin, 2017).

Extracurricular Activities in Public Schools

It is significant toward appraisal the kinds of extracurricular activities presented in the mainstream of the school level (Sax, 2008). There are many extracurricular activities organized by public schools. First, researcher discussed about the assembly activity which is organized in public schools in early morning.

Assembly

Morning assembly is a thing that should renew everyone and fill everybody with excitement until the end of the day. Furthermore, on the off chance that understudies can do it with activities, that is everything thing one can manage. Perhaps the earliest and principal things understudies should do is choosing a host to run the school assembly. Instructors offer this chance to various classes to send their delegate and control the school assembly. Students call different students prior for the morning assembly and have a bunch of activity to invigorate body and brain. Practice is must for each understudy (Ballantyne, 2012).

Sports Activities

The purpose of learning in all states is to emphasize the humanistic opinion, and to qualify individuals to have a bright and strong life. Since the syllabus is quite integrated and does not deliver the pupils with communal, sensitive, and intellectual abilities in teaching -learning procedure, enhancement and improvement of creative and physical activities can be reply to our supple time (Oaks, 2013). Involvement in physical activities benefits learners to mingle, study certain abilities, discover groups and interconnect in a well, strong method. Larson considers that the physical movement is a foremost organization that contains further minor schemes. Through the dissimilar era's physical movement always been portion of individual and communal life of human lives. It shows a countless part in personal relations and communal activities.

Debates

Debating activities can stand-in pupils 'announcement and precarious thinking ability as the learners must consider in a very minor period when talking. They must be capable to distribute their opinions or thoughts established on the truths and indications. There are some meanings of critical thinking serious discerning as reasonable, deep discerning that is attentive on determining what to trust (Tagg, 2015).

Cultural Programs

Cultural program doings are taking place at the institutes, cultural training renders an important involvement to the transmission to awareness, capabilities and morals between persons produce

awareness in terms of principles and morals. These are observed essential for the improvement of one's aims and purposes and improvement of the general superiority of life. Cultural training simplifies in the improvement of abilities and aptitudes, as these are compulsory for the persons to bring out several responsibilities and activities. Traditional education inspires inventive and intrusive arrogances that advantage the persons during their lives Cultural means differ from province to province (Barrett, 2016).

Community Services Activities

Community service activity is a word that is used to define the incorporation of community service into the syllabus in such a way that the communal assistances and the pupils study skills that are related to their upcoming occupation. Service knowledge as an learning practice where learners contribute in an planned service movement in such a way that sees recognized community requirements; and mirror on the service movement in such a way as to improvement more considerate of course comfortable, a wider gratitude of the discipline, and an improved intelligence (Harvey, 2011).

Political Based Activities

Political doings are taking place at institute, the purpose of the political activities is to qualify the pupils to study how well-organized they might be in community life by using their understanding, abilities, and ethics. This might also know as political mastery. The perception of political mastery is clear as getting the understanding, abilities and standards that provision the well-organized and correct conclusions in democratic contribution (Harden, 2009).

Religious Based Activities

Spiritual activity is clear as some movement that mostly encourages or establishes a specific trust in or about a divinity or an final truth. religious performs encourages the well –being of singular, relations. Committed treatment, requesting, or taking part in prepared religion. Faith is belief in an Allah and the doings that are linked with this trust, such as mosque. A religious opinion is a specific structure of trust in a Allah and the activities that are associated with this structure (Gick, 2006).

Leadership Based Activities

Leadership activities deliver that chance to exercise. They are specific or group trainings that agree you to exam and develop your aptitudes (and the aptitudes of your group) in a skillful condition. These trainings are very much like the maneuvers that greatest athletic players track to simulate an authentic struggle. It's significant for pupils to practice management chances throughout their education, to study the skill of structure connotations within groups, describing classify as well as show actual announcement and personal talents (Holyoak, 2013).

Co-curricular Activities in Private School

There are also many co-curricular activities are organized in public school. The first activity is morning assembly.

Assembly

Morning assembly is a thing that should renew everyone and fill everybody with energy until the end of the day. Furthermore, in the event that students can do it with activities, that is everything thing one can manage. Morning assembly is a thing that should renew everyone and fill everybody with energy until the end of the day. What's more, on the off chance that students can do it with

activities, one of the most importantly things students should do is choosing a host to run the school assembly. Educators offer this chance to various classes to send their delegate and control the school assembly that is everything thing one can manage. Students call different students prior for the morning assembly and have a bunch of activity to revive their body and brain. Practice is an unquestionable requirement for each understudy (Rowley, 2007).

Writing Competition

Writing contests are occasions where journalists present their work for survey, ordinarily with expectations of winning an award. There are loads of various types of contests relying upon what kind of work you do some are well defined for brief tales, for instance, or some could need streak fiction composed by or about a specific segment or subject. There are writing contests in schools for papers, film scripts, television pilots, books, novellas, brief tales, sonnets, and more there's most certainly a writing contest for anything you desire to submit (Gligoski, 2012).

Sports

Sports foster the physical as well as mental strength in students. Everyday actual activity is fundamental for students since practice assists students with remaining sound, yet it likewise assists with working on their close to home wellness. Sports ought to be a significant piece of the school educational plan since, supposing that students stay genuinely and truly sound, they can undoubtedly zero in on their examinations. Students should take part in school sports to increment confidence, mental sharpness, and confidence. Sports are significant in schools since it assists with showing different abilities to students like authority, persistence, persistence, collaborations, and interactive abilities (Gisi, 2009).

The sports activities can likewise assist students with performing better in scholastics. The day-to-day proactive tasks assist students with working on their memory and revive their psyches. Teaching drawing to youngsters is fundamental for educators in the grade school classroom as it is a significant ability for kids. Through drawing, you can likewise show kids a great deal of things connected with your desired points them to learn and joining an essential educator instructional class will assist you with learning the techniques for instructing drawing to youngsters comprehensively (Guild, 2007). Students love to investigate their imaginative and creative side and this should be possible by making shapes and designs and through color. Educators will help the children to make writes with colored pencils. Recollect that drawing is an expertise through which students will actually want to communicate their thoughts and what they have realized (Harper, 2011).

Drawing

One of the primary activities you and your students can engage in is drawing. Drawing establishes the foundation for other creative pursuits like composition, modeling, and printmaking while also providing a direct link to reading, writing, and especially math. Drawing is the absolute most open type of workmanship that anyone could hope to find. All you really want (in any case), is a pencil and a piece of paper (Parnell, 2008).

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Debate Competition

A debate is a structured discussion about a topic or objective. A proper debate contains opposing viewpoints and two sides, one of which supports the other's position. These discussions are constrained by newly established rules. Debates might result in the declaration of a victorious party. Debates are frequently used in just social orders to research and decide on topics and problems. The majority of the time, decisions at an executive meeting, formal conference, governing assembly, or local association are made through discussion and argument. Without a question, any discussion of this nature is a debate that may or may not adhere to formal rules. In a school setting, the discussion topic will be determined by the knowledge, skill, and importance outcomes in the educational program (Kuh, 2007).

Painting

At the point when youngsters start to investigate their abilities and fortes, one of the areas some might succeed in is painting. Despite the fact that painting may not be each kid's favorite, it sure has benefits that both you and your kid can gain from together. Among the different angles that painting permits you to cover, the absolute most noteworthy advantages coordinated with painting will be Painting can assist your kids with communicating their feelings or sentiments. They can express their ideas without using words by using a variety of hues. (Maher, 2012). Painting gives children access to an enjoyable and energizing learning opportunity. Painting helps children develop coordination, a crucial skill for their age.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was descriptive in nature and survey method was used for the study. The population of the study was consisted on ten (10) public and thirteen (13) private secondary schools in Pretoria city, Gautang province, South Africa. The researcher selected two hundred and fifty-six (256) teachers from private and public secondary schools' level of Pretoria city. The study tool used to gather data from secondary school teachers in both public and private schools was a questionnaire. Two educational specialists from Institute of Online and Distance Learning College of Education University of South Africa validated the questionnaire. Pilot tests were performed by the researcher to evaluate the instrument's precision and usefulness. The researcher gave the questionnaire to 20 secondary teachers as part of a pilot project. The researcher took into account the issues brought up by the pilot testing subjects. The researcher directly gathered the data from secondary school teachers in the Pretoria city schools. Utilizing a Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) the data was examined. Simple mean, frequency, and proportion were used by the researcher to analyze the data.

RESULTS

Table 1: Mean analysis of Co-curricular Activities in Public Schools regarding Assembly

Statements	N	Mean
School morning assembly freshens students for whole day	100	4.75
Morning assembly promotes a positive school culture	100	4.42
Morning assembly develops feeling of unity among students and teachers	100	4.74
Morning assembly could be used for teaching social behavior	100	4.61

Table 1 shows the Meta score of assembly. The table further represented that the mean score of School morning assembly freshens students for whole day; N=100, M=4.75, Morning assembly promotes a positive school culture; N=100, M= 4.42, Morning assembly develops feeling of unity among students and teachers; N=100, M= 4.74, Morning assembly could be used for teaching social behavior; N=100, M= 4.61. Furthermore, results directed that Morning assembly develops feeling of unity among students and teachers has the highest mean score in mean analysis of assembly.

Table 2: Mean analysis of sports activities

Statements	N	Mean
Sports activities develop physical strength of students	100	4.62
Sports helps to improve students' physical fitness	100	4.55
Sports enhance the confidence level of students	100	4.70
Sports help to teach leadership skills to students	100	4.30

Table 2 shows the Meta score of sports. The table further represented that the mean score of Sports activities develop physical strength of students; N=100, M=4.62, Sports helps to improve students' physical fitness; N=100, M= 4.55, Sports enhance the confidence level of students; N=100, M= 4.70, Sports help to teach leadership skills to students; N=100, M= 4.30. Furthermore, results directed that Morning assembly develops feeling of unity among students and teachers has the highest mean score in mean analysis of assembly.

Table 3: Mean analysis of cultural activities

Statements	N	Mean
Cultural activities develop the physical health of students	100	4.49
Cultural program develops communication skills in students	100	4.60
Cultural program removes fear of public speaking	100	3.85
Cultural program enhances self-confidence of students	100	4.38

Table 3 shows the Meta score of Cultural activities. The table further represented that the mean score of Cultural activities develop the physical health of students; N=100, M=4.49, Cultural program develops communication skills in students; N=100, M= 4.60, Cultural program removes fear of public speaking; N=100, M= 3.85, Cultural program enhances self-confidence of students; N=100, M= 4.38. Furthermore, results directed that Cultural activities develop the physical health of students has the highest mean score in mean analysis of cultural activities.

Table 4: Mean analysis of religious activities

Statements	N	Mean
Religious values contribute to development of personal morality	100	4.86
Religious education serves as a respect for diversity	100	4.75
Religious activities promote kindness among students	100	4.64
Students show polite behavior with other students	100	4.88

Table 4 shows the Meta score of religious activities. The table further represented that the mean score of religious values contribute to development of personal morality; N=100, M=4.86, Religious education serves as a respect for diversity; N=100, M= 4.75, Religious activities promote kindness among students; N=100, M= 4.64, Students show polite behavior with other students; N=100, M= 4.88. Furthermore, results directed that Students show polite behavior with other students has the highest mean score in mean analysis of religious activities.

Mean analysis of co-curricular activities in private schools

Table 5: Mean analysis of Painting

Statements	N	Mean
Painting promotes the creativity of children	156	4.72
Painting helps the children to explore color	156	4.73
Painting helps the children to express their emotion	156	4.69
Painting encourages the creativity among students	156	4.57

Table 5 shows the Meta score of paintings. The table further represented that the mean score of Painting promotes the creativity of children; N=156, M=4.72, Painting helps the children to explore color; N=156, M= 4.73, Painting helps the children to express their emotion; N=156, M= 4.69, Painting encourages the creativity among students; N=156, M= 4.57. Furthermore, results directed that Painting helps the children to explore color has the highest mean score in mean analysis of painting.

Table 6: Mean analysis of writing

Statements	N	Mean
Writing helps the students to express their feelings to the other	156	4.66
Writing enhances critical thinking in the students	156	4.28
Writing improves the communication skills of students	156	4.48
Writing helps in organizing thoughts of students	156	4.38

Table 6 shows the Meta score of writing. The table further represented that the mean score of Writing helps the students to express their feelings to the other; N=156, M=4.66, Writing enhances critical thinking in the students; N=156, M= 4.28, Writing improves the communication skills of students; N=156, M= 4.48, Writing helps in organizing thoughts of students; N=156, M= 4.38. Furthermore, results directed that Writing helps the students to express their feelings to the other has the highest mean score in mean analysis of assembly.

Table 7: Mean analysis of Drawing

Statements	N	Mean
Drawing develops the motor skills in the children	156	4.40
Drawing builds children's self-esteem	156	4.36
Drawing increases children's artistic knowledge	156	4.48
Drawing develops different ideas in the mind of students	156	4.28

Table 7 shows the Meta score of Drawing. The table further represented that the mean score of Drawing develops the motor skills in the children; N=156, M=4.40, Drawing builds children's self-esteem; N=156, M= 4.36, Drawing increases children's artistic knowledge; N=156, M= 4.48, Drawing develops different ideas in the mind of students; N=156, M= 4.28. Furthermore, results directed that Drawing increases children's artistic knowledge has the highest mean score in mean analysis of Drawing.

Table 8: Mean analysis of Debate competition

Statements	N	Mean
Debate competition promotes problem solving skills in students	156	4.42
Debate competition helps students to build links between words and ideas	156	4.55
Debate competition develops the innovative thinking in students	156	4.37
Debate competition helps students to make concepts more meaningful	156	4.55

Table 8 shows the Meta score of Debate competition. The table further represented that the mean score of Debate competition promotes problem solving skills in students; N=156, M=4.42, Debate competition helps students to build links between words and ideas; N=156, M= 4.55, Debate competition develops the innovative thinking in students; N=156, M= 4.37, Debate competition helps students to make concepts more meaningful; N=156, M= 4.55. Furthermore, results directed that Debate competition helps students to build links between words and ideas has the highest mean score in mean analysis of Debate competition.

DISCUSSION

Co-curricular activities play a crucial role in the development of students, beyond academic education. The aforementioned conclusions of the study emphasize the significance of various co-curricular activities in shaping the overall growth and development of students.

Morning assembly is an important part of school life and serves as an opportunity for students and teachers to come together, share thoughts, and promote unity. A study conducted by [Kaur and Singh \(2021\)](#) found that morning assembly has a positive impact on the mental health of students and promotes a sense of belongingness. Another study by [Akhtar and Raja \(2020\)](#) found that morning assembly can also enhance students' discipline and punctuality. Sports activities are important for the physical development of students. They can help students develop leadership skills, teamwork, and confidence, in addition to improving their physical fitness. A study by [Singh and Singh \(2019\)](#) found that participation in sports can improve the academic performance of students. Cultural activities, on the other hand, promote communication skills and physical health. A study by [Oben et al. \(2021\)](#) found that cultural activities can improve students' mental health and self-esteem.

Religious education is important for the development of personal morality and respect for diversity. A study by [Tanveer et al. \(2021\)](#) found that religious education can have a positive impact on students' social and emotional well-being. Another study by [Shahzad and Hassan \(2021\)](#) found that religious education can promote tolerance and understanding among students. Painting, drawing, and writing are important for the creative development of students. They can help students express their emotions and organize their thoughts, leading to improved critical thinking and communication skills. A study by [Kim \(2020\)](#) found that creative activities can have a positive impact on students' emotional regulation and self-esteem. Debate competitions can promote innovative thinking and problem-solving skills in students. A study by [Ahmad et al. \(2019\)](#) found that participation in debate competitions can enhance students' critical thinking and communication skills, as well as their self-confidence.

In conclusion, co-curricular activities play a crucial role in the overall growth and development of students. The aforementioned conclusions of the study highlight the importance of various co-curricular activities in shaping students' mental, physical, and emotional well-being. It is crucial for schools to encourage and facilitate these activities to ensure the holistic development of students

CONCLUSIONS

1. It is concluded that school morning assembly freshens students for whole day. Morning assembly promotes a positive school culture and develops feeling of unity among students and teachers.
2. It is concluded that sports activities develop physical strength of students. Sports also helps to teach leadership skills and improve students' physical fitness. It also enhances the confidence level of students. Moreover, cultural activities also develop communication skills and physical health of students.
3. It is concluded that religious values contribute to development of personal morality. Religious education also serves as a respect for diversity and promotes kindness among students. Moreover, students show polite behavior with other students.
4. It is concluded that painting promotes the creativity of children. Painting helps the children to explore color and to express their emotion. It also encourages creativity among students.
5. It is concluded that writing helps the students to organize thoughts and express their feelings. Writing enhances critical thinking and communication skills of students.
6. It is concluded that drawing develops different ideas and the motor skills in the children. Drawing also builds the children's self-esteem and artistic knowledge. Moreover, debate competition promotes innovative thinking and problem-solving skills in students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. It is recommended that teachers may make the morning assembly a center of interest by giving it strength and spirit. Physical education teachers may ensure that all students participate in the morning assembly, considering students' weaknesses.
2. In order to get skills on extracurricular activities, with proper skilled teachers it will be easily to implement extracurricular activities in school because they can be aware on how to organize and supervise extracurricular for the benefits of the students.

3. School administrators may priorities cooperation, support among peers, and trust in order to foster a strong school culture. Therefore, it is essential that school administrators include all interested parties in the creation and implementation of school management initiatives.
4. It is recommended that to improve students' moral behavior, practical religious education must be incorporated into all courses. Subject matter in primary school may include elements of religion and morality.
5. To improve children's' art, drawing and painting may be made an integral part of the curriculum and teachers helps the children to draw on different shapes in the class on the regular basis especial in public schools.
6. To better perform in writing, Students may practice their grammar and words ever-increasingly. They may pay close attention while learning how to enunciate words in class or at home. Students should also pay attention to the text's organization and Make mental notes and recaps.
7. The ability to correctly draw the shapes of different objects in the process of drawing, teachers may encourage students to practice the landscape, the environment, and the realities of life and achieve the use of different materials in painting.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, M. S., Zafar, S. A., & Ali, A. (2019). Effectiveness of debate competitions on critical thinking skills: A comparative study of male and female students. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 34(2), 309-330.
- Ahmed, B. E. (2014). Role of Teacher Related Factors in Basic Education: A Case of Govt. Secondary Schools in Karachi, Pakistan. *Journal of Management Information*, 1(4), 107-115.
- Akhtar, N., & Raja, M. A. (2020). The impact of school assembly on students' discipline and punctuality. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 7(2), 67-81.
- Aslam, M. G. (2010). What Can Teachers Do to Raise Pupil Achievement? *Economics of Education Review*, 30(3), 559-574.
- Astin, A. W. (2017). The methodology of research on college impact. *Sociology of Education*, 4(3), 223-254.
- Barrett, H. P. (2016). Using electronic portfolios for classroom assessment. *Technology Connected Newsletter*, 13(2), 4-6.
- Ballantyne, R. W. (2012). Developing reflection on practice through journal writing: Impacts of variations in the focus and level of feedback. *Teachers and teaching*, 8(1), 171-196.
- Gajjar, N. B. (2014). Co-Curricular Activities and Value Education. *International Journal of Research in all subjects*, 3(1), 15-20.
- Gligoski, E. S. (2012). Motivating the learner: Mozilla's Open Badges program. *Access to knowledge*, 4(1), 23-38.
- Gisi, S. D. (2009). Adult undergraduate students: What role does college involvement. *NASPA Journal*, 38(1), 99-121.
- Gick, M. P. (2006). Analogical problem solving. *Cognitive Psychology*, 1(2), 306-355.
- Holyoak, K. O. (2013). Schema induction and analogical transfer. *Cognitive Psychology*, 1(5), 1-38.
- Guild, P. B. (2007). Where do the learning theories overlap? . *Educational Leadership*, 1(2), 34

90.

- Harvey, L. H. (2011). Transforming work experience in higher education. *British Educational Research Journal*, 2(7), 269-290.
- Harden, R. H. (2009). Portfolios as a method of student assessment. *Medical Teacher*, 2(3), 535-551.
- Harper, S. G. (2011). Using qualitative methods to assess student trajectories and college impact. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 1(3), 45-56.
- Husain, F. P. (2012). The Effectiveness of Co-curricular Activities on Academic Achievements of Secondary School Students in District Abbottabad Pakistan . *Journal of Education and Practice*, 1(3), 44-49.
- Karim, R. L. (2011). Facilities of Government & Private Secondary School Teachers of Karachi. *A comparative Analysis. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and social sciences*, 1(2), 191-201.
- Kaur, H., & Singh, N. (2021). Impact of morning assembly on mental health and academic performance of students. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(8), 53-62.
- Kim, S. (2020). The effects of creative activity programs on children's emotional regulation and self-esteem: A systematic review. *Journal of Child Health Care*, 24(3), 409-422.
- Kuh, G. H. (2007). Myths and misconceptions about using qualitative methods in assessment. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 1(3), 5-15.
- Maher, C. P. (2012). Inclusion of pupils with SENs into mainstream Physical Education –potential research ideas to explore issues of engagement. . *Journal of Qualitative Research in Sports Studies*, 6(1), 35-48.
- Memon, R. G. (2007). Education in Pakistan: The key issues, problems and the new challenges. *Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 47-55.
- Muhammad, I. Z. (2012). Public versus Private Secondary Schools, A qualitative comparison. *Journal of Research and Reflections in Education*, 6(1), 40-49.
- Mukesh, K. U. (2013). Role Of a Teacher In Organizing Co-Curricular Activities In School. *Golden Research Thoughts*, 3(1), 1-29.
- Oaks, D. J. (2013). Student employee development in students affairs. *Research and Practice in Assessment*, 1(8), 55-68.
- Oben, F. M., Tanyi, E. K., Mbu, E. T., & Mbu, L. E. (2021). Cultural activities and the mental health of students in higher education institutions. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 11(1), 67-77.
- Parnell, 1.-4. (2008). Structures for facilitating student reflection. *College Teaching*, 5(7), 15-22.
- Rowley, J. D. (2007). E-Learning: The student experience. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 38(4), 560-573.
- Sax, L. J. (2008). How undergraduates are affected by service participation. *Journal of College Student Development*, 39(3), 251-263.
- Shahzad, S., & Hassan, S. (2021). Role of religious education in promoting tolerance and understanding among students. *Pakistan Journal*.
- Tagg, J. M. (2015). From teaching to learning: A new paradigm for undergraduate education. *Change*, 27(6), 13-25.
- Yaseen, M. Z. (2017). An Empirical Study on the Role of Parents in Academic Achievement of Children in Private Schools of Karachi. *Journal of Criminology and Sociology*, 6(1), 84-92.